

Developing a Guiding Model of Educational Leadership in Higher Education: BELTEI International University

SAN Soeurn; Dr. Paradise ROS; Dr. IN Channy
BELTEI International University, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

Abstract

The primary purpose of this study is to investigate the Developing a Guiding Model of Educational Leadership in Higher Education at BELTEI International University. The participants were 35 of selection (lecturers, managers, team leaders working at (BIU). The study uses both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The data were collected using a questionnaire which includes 55 items from the five sections and the participants spent approximately 5- 10 minutes to respond in the questionnaire. The data obtained were analyzed automatically in Google form as the percentage to determine the participants' ages, genders, working places, their experiences and attitudes towards the importance of educational leadership in Higher educations. The findings in the study showed that the characteristic, skill, knowledge and attitude which good leaders should be and practice to develop their ability and knowledge about leadership. The study benefits to students to enlarge better understanding of leadership skills effectively by examining of what determined through the concept of lecturers/managers/directors. Finally, it also gives benefits to researcher to gain more experiences about the guiding or modeling of educational leadership.

Key word: Guiding model, Educational leadership, Higher education

Introduction

Today's well-managed firms require individuals who are good and successful leaders who are enthusiastic about their work, working ability to interact both inside and between organizations. At the same time, it is critical to be able to develop relationships by willingly cooperating (Participation cooperation) which leads the organization to progress and reduce conflicts in coordination with the people around. Therefore, a new leader to be successful requires constant study. Learn to keep up with the changing conditions both economically and socially that are constantly raging. An effective leader must be able to enable colleagues to do quality and full work in the workplace. In the changing world, management must be a leader who can solve problems that may arise in the future by encouraging others to trust and accept their way of working (Santivong, 2550). In addition, the management should perform the duty of committing the work of the group members to help them succeed. Educational leadership has become a priority in education policy programs worldwide. It plays a crucial role in refining school outcomes by influencing the motivations and capabilities of the teachers, as well as the school climate and environment. Operative educational leadership is vital to improve the efficiency and pertinence of education. Educational leadership responsibilities should be adequately defined through an understanding of the practices that are required to make an improvement in teaching and learning. In many countries,

the school administrators and the principals have heavy work- loads, they are over-burdened with work. Most of these individuals are reaching the retirement age and it is difficult to find leaders with capabilities and competencies. Educational leadership functions can contribute in making provision of guidance on the main characteristics, tasks and responsibilities of proficient leaders in the field of education (Beatriz, Deborah, & Hopkins, 2008). The role of educational leaders has been undergoing many changes in the era of globalization due to diverse needs and expectations of the stakeholders of education. This increases the need for professional development of educational leaders to fulfill their roles. Educational leaders have high impact on shaping school culture, school improvement, student learning, and achievement, so that their professional development is critical to their continued success as leaders.

Problems

Even though, BELTEI International University has its own guild model of educational leadership but it still be used in general. It is shown to be a problem for BELTEI's students with their model leadership, and one more problem is that sometimes lecturers also use difference model of leadership. So, it makes students confuse what are they going to use and which model of leadership is the best for them to improve their ability in daily life. In this case, they used many models which are flexible. So, it makes the students confuse that what model is the best model for them to improve or which model should they have used into their real life especially the benefit of using the leadership effectively. As a result, they will feel disreputable with leadership in the classroom. In this research will guide lecturer, professor to glance the importance of being using their leadership effectively and students will be trustworthy on their learning outcomes. As we know that the work of school leaders is

complex and challenging. Even in non-pandemic times, school leaders are regularly pressured to make decisions or solve problems without sufficient time, resources or knowledge. More often than not, this can lead to compromise and pragmatism over a perfect outcome.

Questions

Therefore, the purpose of this research is to look at BELTEI International University's guild model of educational leadership in higher education. It aims to answer the following research question in particular:

1. What are the best models of used educational leadership?
2. How do you develop a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education?
3. Why educational leadership should be reputable in Higher Education?

Significance

Today's well-managed firms require individuals who are good and successful leaders who are enthusiastic about their work, working ability to interact both inside and between organizations. The findings of this study are expected to provide useful information for the following key persons to take into account. First, the results of this study benefit to BELTEI International University to identify the model of educational leadership and to develop a guiding model of educational leadership for leader teams, manager's team, lecturer and directors who are involved in BELTEI International University. As we know, good leadership in schools is the practice of encouraging and enabling school-wide teaching expertise in order to achieve a strong rate of progress for all learners. Students who have ability in leadership can gain better skills than those who are unskilled. It might help students to improve their leadership by using this guiding model, so the basic of good leadership should be taught and practiced from the early years

of learning. By the way, the result of the study can identify the challenges faced by students and the solutions to solve the problems during using the guiding model. When the students clearly understand the difficulties and obstacles in using the guiding model, they can be ready to find the solutions to make their study successful. It's like the compass to guide students toward success in leadership using short time but they can gain high efficiency and quality.

Second, the result of this study is also important for the enhancement a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education in term of the 21st century. In addition, the result also helps teachers to select the right approach model to help students because there are many approaches in providing leadership. It means that strategies need to be selected carefully in order to contribute most effective to students learning. Moreover, it benefits to leader, management team, teacher to assess suitability and the possibility of students trustworthy on their learning outcomes.

Finally, findings of this study have the most significant contribution to me and all the students in next generation to study with these different focus and statistical method.

Research Scope

This research will be conducted at BELTEI International University (Campus 1 and Campus 2) a). Campus 1 locates in Toul Sleng (#21, St. 360, Sangkat Boeung Kengkang, Khan Boeung Kengkang, Phnom penh), And b). Campus 2 locates in Chom Chao (#151, National high way 3, Sangkat Chom Chao, Khan Posenchey, Phnom penh) to make this propose by following the above objectives. I would like to select 35 participants which include lecturers/professors, management teams and team leaders are selected as the target population (Sample size). And the data collections are used as use a qualitative and quantitative.

Literature Review

Leadership is a hot-button issue these days. Reformers depend on it. The public believes that it is what schools need more of. And private sector CEOs think they know exactly what it is and are anxious to share that knowledge with the "poor unwashed masses" of educational leaders. It is not surprising, then, that so many people are trying to make a living peddling their latest insights about effective educational leadership. Indeed, leadership by adjective is a growth industry. We have instructional leadership, transformational leadership, moral leadership, constructivist leadership, servant leadership, cultural leadership we even have primal leadership (D. Goleman, R. Boyatzis, A. McKEE, 2002). A few of these qualify as leadership theories and several are actually tested leadership theories. But most are actually just slogans. Consider, for example, the term "instructional leadership": it typically serves as a synonym for whatever the speaker means by "good" leadership with almost no reference to models of instructional leadership that have some conceptual coherence and a body of evidence testing their effects on organizations and students. With all this confusion about the concept of leadership in our environment, we might be persuaded to think that hard evidence about what is good or successful or effective leadership in education organizations is lacking or at least contradictor we would be wrong. We actually know a great deal about the leadership behaviors, practices, or actions that are helpful in improving the impact of districts and schools on the student outcomes that we value. "True leadership is the ability to influence people to achieve a better result for an organization or group," says career coach Kathleen Brady.

In the workplace, a leader's influence can be reflected in employee

happiness, a healthy bottom line, a culture of innovation, positive social change, and more. For example, data shows that 70% of workforce engagement, defined as the level of commitment and connection an employee has with their workplace, is influenced by managers. Leadership opportunities are not reserved for the executive suite. Leaders and managers exist at every level of an organization, from staff that steer small departmental projects to those who oversee massive global endeavours. It's smart to prepare for your next leadership opportunity by understanding the leadership model that works best for you. A leadership model is a theoretical framework for how best to manage employees. It typically suggests a corresponding response style to employee and organizational needs that has proven useful in that model. Leadership models provide a useful structure for defining the

management methods that fit your work style and personality. Knowing your personal approach to leadership both where it comes from and where you want to go with it creates a standard from which you can make adjustments and improvements to maximize your efficacy and impact.

Leadership models don't exist in a vacuum; however, you may pull elements from more than one model, or you may shift among models over time or in different settings. Although leadership models are similar to leadership styles, these are two separate concepts. While the model serves as the conceptual structure to explain what makes a leader great, the style represents the pattern of leadership behaviours they exhibit in pursuit of that greatness.

Research Models

Key Professional Practices through the Leadership Requirements

Leading teaching and learning	Developing self and others	Leading improvement, innovation and change	Leading the management of the school	Engaging and working with the community
1).creating a positive culture of challenge and support 2).enabling effective teaching that promotes enthusiastic, independent learners, committed to lifelong learning 3).developing a culture of effective teaching 4).leading, designing and managing the quality of teaching and learning	1).building a professional learning community focused on continuous improvement of teaching and learning 2).managing performance, effective continuing professional learning and feedback 3).supporting all staff to achieve high standards and develop their leadership	1).producing and implementing clear, evidence-based improvement plans and policies for the development of the school 2). leading and managing innovation and change to ensure the vision and strategic plan is put into action across the school and that its goals and intentions are realized.	1).using a range of data management methods and technologies to ensure that the school's resources and staff are efficiently organized and managed 2).delegating tasks to members of staff 3).monitoring and meeting of accountabilities 4).effectively collaborating with school boards, governing bodies, parents and	1).embracing inclusion and helping build a culture of high expectations that takes account of the richness and diversity of the wider school community 2).developing and maintaining positive partnerships with students, families and careers and the wider school community 3).taking account of students' spiritual, moral,

<p>5).setting high expectations for the whole school through careful collaborative planning, monitoring and reviewing</p> <p>6).setting high standards of behavior and attendance, encouraging active engagement and a strong student voice.</p>	<p>capacity</p> <p>4).treating people fairly and with respect</p> <p>5). modelling effective leadership and being committed to own ongoing professional development, personal health and well-being.</p>		<p>others.</p>	<p>social and physical health and well-being</p> <p>4).promoting sound lifelong learning from preschool through to adult life</p> <p>5).recognizing the multicultural nature of Australia’s people</p> <p>6).fostering understanding and reconciliation with Indigenous cultures.</p>
--	--	--	----------------	---

Gaps in The Literature: Since the 1990s, education systems have gone through a range of phases. Systems have moved away from central management of education inputs by ministries of education. There was a shift towards decentralization and greater school autonomy in a search for school improvement. Decentralization was coupled with an increased focus on accountability and results in education (Fullan, 2009; Hattie, 2015; Malone, 2013; OECD, 2014; Salhberg, 2010). This gave way to school leaders adopting a more managerial role, focusing on delivering on school objectives more directly, especially in English speaking countries. This was followed with the introduction of more national and international evaluations at the student and system level at the beginning of the 21st century, in line with trends towards of increased public

accountability and decentralization. The introduction of evaluations also reflected a shift from inputs to outcomes. At this time, the school leader role shifted towards instructional leadership, focusing more directly on school outcomes.

Research Framework

The literature in different theoretical models to examine the developing a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education has helped the researcher understand the suitability of the models and frameworks of the study and literature review; the researcher has designed this analytical framework of the study. This analytical framework presents the relationship among variables as shown in the following figure.

Figure 1: Research Framework

Methodology

According to many social sciences, investigative research seeks to discover how people get along in the setting under question, what meanings they give to their actions, and what problems concern them. The goal is to learn what is going on, and to explore social phenomena without obvious expectations. In addition, experimental research is usually conducted because a problem has not yet been clearly definite. It helps determine the best research design, data collection method and selection of subjects. Given its fundamental nature, exploratory research often concludes that a seeming problem does not actually exist. Therefore, in order to gain a greater understanding of the developing a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education in BELTEI International University, Phnom Penh, an investigative research design observing both qualitative and quantitative data will be hired.

- (a) Two campus lectures/professors

- (a) Two campuses directors
- (b) Twelve Deans of Faculties
- (c) Twelve Vice-Deans of faculties
- (d) Academic office managers.

The two campuses are classified as the location where the 12 faculties of my research are, namely:

- Faculty of Business Administration
- Faculty of Finance and Banking
- Faculty of Economics
- Faculty of Law
- Faculty of International Relations
- Faculty of Education, Arts, and Humanities
- Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality
- Faculty of Information Technology and Science
- Faculty of Digital Technology and Telecommunication
- Faculty of Engineering
- Faculty of Architecture
- Faculty of Civil Aviation

Data Collection Instruments

This research will mainly make use of a survey questionnaire that had been

manufactured based on the proposed framework and in contemplation of the objectives set forth by the study. The instrument that was used for collecting data was a questionnaire that was made available to the participants in both online and printed format from two campuses. The questionnaire had to find answers to four sections of questions:

- **Section 1.** Seek to see and describe about the Quality Assessment as a guiding Model of Educational Leadership, Skill.
- **Section 2.** Seek to see and describe about knowledge and attitude toward to educational leadership.
- **Section 3.** Seek to see and describe about High quality and paid job in educational leadership.
- **Section 4.** Seek to see and describe about developing a guiding model of educational leadership need to be develop. To make sure this study get much more validity and reliable, survey procedures and steps in Delphi method are the supports used.

- **Survey Procedures and Steps in Delphi method**

- **Characteristic:**

- 1) anonymity => reduce dominant effect to respondents,
- 2) geographically dispersion,
- 3) e-communication to solicit/exchange information,
- 4) Controlled feedback a) reduce noise effect, b) well organized summary of prior interaction => (revise & insight), 5) stat analysis =>objective

- Process: 3 rounds = sufficient (up to 4 Rounds).

- Round 1: Open-ended Qnaire to survey for R2, if extensive LR => can use structure Qnaire;
- Round 2: 2nd Qnaires to review item summarized based on info provided in R1 => to rate/ rank-order/ priorities. In this round areas

of disagreement & agreement identified

- Round 3: a Qnaire summarize item rates in previous round & ask to review or specify reason for remaining outside the consensus
- Round 4: (often final), list of remaining item, their ratings, minority opinion & item achieving consensus, final opportunity to revise judgment

- **Using 6 approaches/ steps:**

- 1) Set up a Delphi process: Set goals; expert selection (heterogeneous); Consideration (Geographical dispersion, cost, time, disagreements amongst experts); Survey (open-ended Qs, introduction/closure, 30 mn time restrict, pilot the survey)
- 2) Develop items & response scales: Decide on No. of issues to be explored; Create questions (clear, concise, group by explored issues, start with simple Qs, clear response formats (categorical, ordinal/interval/ratio scales; 5 and 7-point scale)
- 3) Online delivery mode: E-mail/ telegram/ google web-based, or real-time (tele-conference)
- 4) Feedback to panelists: Median responses, range, inter-quartile range of responses for each question; elicit & utilize respondents' rationales for their view/ ranking; Develop & apply a criterion of consensus
- 5) Prevent & deal with panelist drop-out: Use self-rated experts (as they tend not to drop out), Consider using social/ financial rewards; Use personal communications with panelists
- 6) Analyze & present Delphi data: Descriptive statistics; use of graphical representations of data; integrate Delphi results with knowledge of the broader picture

provided by other including quantitative research

Statistical Treatment and Analysis

Analysis and interpretation of collected data will be done both in qualitative and quantitative measure. Through the use of Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 25, data will be encoded; tables and graphs will be constructed, interpreted and analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively following the order of the research questions.

Particularly, research questions one (1), two (2), three (3), and four (4) will be treated and analyzed quantitatively like the use of frequencies and percentages; while research question five (5) will be treated and analyzed qualitatively.

Sampling Techniques

To ensure the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire, two general steps will be undertaken. First, the appended survey questionnaire will be presented before the research panel members assigned by the Faculty of Education, Arts and Humanities. This will then be revised according to the panel's scrutiny, suggestions and recommendations as manifested during the proposal defense.

The second step to ensure validity and reliability, the revised questionnaire will be further submitted to a three-member panel of experts for content validation. The panel will be composed of two (2) holders of Master Degree in Educational Administration, and one (1) holder of Bachelor of Art in Foreign Affairs. They will be purposely considered on the bases of their professional or educational qualifications, wide range of experience as school administrators and managers, and finally, on the nature of their current job assignments. Having considered them as "experts" in their respective field, they will be asked to evaluate each question/ statement whether it is: Very Relevant (4), Relevant (3), Less Relevant (2) or Not Relevant (1). The ratings of the panel of experts will then be

subjected to a statistical treatment using the Yamane formula for determining the sample size is given to determine the degree of agreement among the raters for each item using the formula:

- Sample Size and Sampling Designs: This research has been working with a finite population and if the population size it known, the Slovin Formula for determining the sample size is given by:
- Formula of sample size: Slovin Formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n = Sample size

N = population size

e = Margin of error (0.05)

- Suppose the researcher wishes to interview the participants at BELTEI International University where contains for 200 participants. How many participants do the researcher interview?

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{38}{1 + 38(0.05)^2} = 34.703 = 35$$

Thus, the researcher interviews only 35 participants who are represented the 38 participants (Population).

- The Delphi Pilot survey was conducted from November 30, 2024 to December 05, 2024.

- The Delphi Round 1 was conducted from December 15, 2024 to February 11, 2025, followed by the analysis to formulate for Round 2

- The Delphi Round 2 was conducted from February 09, 2025 to May 15, 2025, followed by the analysis to formulate for Round 3

- The Delphi Round 3 was conducted from May 15, 2025 to June 21, 2025, followed by the analysis

- During the survey, ethical issues for privacy and confidentiality were ensured for the participant.

- Delphi technique: Round 1, 2 and Round 3 online questionnaires

- Using 5-point scales

Source: Author's own view with adaptation from: Katherin F.H, et al., 2020; Nicholas A.C et al., 2021; Snica F.H, et al., 2019; Arah H. et al., 2014; Swana V. el al., 2019

Triangulation and cross-check

Using Cronbach alpha to test the internal validity

Where k is the No. of variables & r is the mean of the inter-item

Correlations.

$\alpha \geq 0.9$: Excellent $0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$: Good $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$: Acceptable
 $0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$: Questionable $0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$: Poor $\alpha < 0.5$: Unacceptable

The finding of the questionnaires showed that respondents of all ages (below 25 through to above 45) were represented, the age bracket from below to 25 years old have 8 (22.9%), from 26 to 30 years old 9 (25.7%), from 31 to 35 years old 12 (34.3%), from 36 to 45 years old 3 (8.6%), the oldest age bracket 45 and above years old 3 (8.6%) (**show in figure 6.1**). Like the result shows in (**figure 6.2**), the proportion of gender was about male 24 (68,6%) and female 11 (31.4%). With regard to the participants in this study, almost participants work at BELTEI International University, campus 1 (Tuol sleng) has 25 (71.4%), while at campus 2 (Chomchao) has 1 (2.9%) and some of them has worked in both two campuses have 9 (25.7%) (**show in figure 6.3**). Moreover, most participants teach/work in faculty of Educations, Arts and Humanities 31 (91.6%), in Business 1 (2.1%), in Finance and Banking 1 (2.1%), in International Relation 1 (2.1%) and teach in all faculty 1 (2.1%)

The survey can observe that most participants take the position in charge of teaching 16 (45.7%), in charge as Dean/Vice Dean 7 (20%), in charge as Director/ deputy director 2 (5.7%) and other position 10 (28.6%). Most of the participants have been working/teaching at

BIU from 2 to 3 years 15 (42.9%), from 4 to 5 years 4 (11.4%), from 1 and less then around 5 (14.3%), from 6 years and more than 6 years around 11 (31.4%).

$$\alpha = \frac{kr}{1+(k-1)r}$$

According to the survey, the researcher find out that most respondents think that Educational Leadership is important "Yes" 34 (97.1)% while "No" has 1 (2.9%). Most of them have agree that educational leadership is very important because education can change the world, education can help people find way to improve themselves, leadership can lead people/follower and manage people to work together when they get higher position, education.

Based on the survey, the result shows that 25 respondents (71.4%) have ever been trained to be as a leader before they start teaching from 6 months to more than 5 years while 10 respondents (28.6%) have never been trained. Most of respondents 23 (65.7%) have worked as a leader for 2 to 3 years while there are some people have worked 1 years and less then around 9 (25.7%) and from 6 to more than around 3 (8.6%) .

Section II Quality Assessment as a guiding Model of Educational Leadership

A. Model 1: Characteristic of leadership

Based on 35 respondents, the result shown that 18 respondents strongly agree that "Leaders should be Flexible and do as a model or as an example for others", while other 15 respondents agree, 1 respondent neutral and 1 respondent disagree. Additionally, there are 17 respondents Strongly agree that "Leaders have a long-term, deep impact on their communities and nations", whereas other 12 respondents agree but another 5 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are

16 respondents agree that “Leaders can and do make a difference in the strength of their institutions”, while 13 respondents responded strongly agree, another 5 respondents neutral and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Besides that, there are 18 respondents agree that “Leaders also practice key behaviors on a regular basis in order to strengthen the positive impact of these qualities”, while other 9 respondents strongly agree, 6 respondents neutral and another 1 respondent responds disagree and 1 respondent strongly disagree. In other hand, there are 15 respondents agree that “Leaders are self-aware and prioritize personal development” while 13 respondents strongly Agree, 5 respondents respond neutral, whereas 2 respondents are strongly disagreed. It was also observed that, there are 18 respondents agree that “Leaders can and do make a difference in the strength of their institutions”, 10 respondents strongly agree, while other 6 respondents selected “Neutral”, 1 respondent are strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 16 participants “Agree” that “leader adapt to whether an individual or group is ready, willing and able to take specific action” and “Strongly Agree” was chosen by 12 respondents, meanwhile 6 participants are neutral and 1 participant strongly disagree. Beside that there are 21 participants “Agree” that “Leaders consider the ethical consequences of the decisions that they make for both their customers and their teams”, 8 respondents strongly Agree, while 4 participants are neutral and 1 participant disagree, whereas 1 respondent strongly Disagree. Lastly, there are 15 respondents responded agree that “Leaders are able to clearly communicate with individual, business units, the entire company, and to stakeholder outside the organization” while respondents are strongly agreed, 6 more respondents are neutral, 1 respondent disagree and the other 1 are strongly disagree.

B. Model 2: Role of good leader

Based on 35 respondents, the result shown that 16 respondents agree that “Leaders should engage in honest, open communication”, while other 13 respondents strongly agrees, 4 respondents are neutral, other 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent are strongly disagreed. Additionally, there are 21 respondents Strongly agree that “Leaders should connect with your team members”, whereas other 8 respondents agree but another 4 respondents neutral, other 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 17 respondents agree that “Leaders should encourage personal and professional growth”, while 12 respondents responded strongly agree, another 3 respondents neutral, 1 respondent disagree and other 2 respondents strongly disagree. Besides that, there are 16 respondents strongly agree that “Leaders should keep a positive attitude”, while other 12 respondents agree, 6 respondents neutral and another 1 respondent strongly disagree. In other hand, there are 17 respondents strongly agree that “Leaders should teach employees instead of giving orders” while 13 respondents Agree, 4 respondents are neutral, whereas 1 respondent is strongly Disagree. It was also observed that, there are 14 respondents agree that “Leaders should set clear employees’ goal and expectations”, 13 respondents strongly agree, while other 7 respondents selected “Neutral” and 1 respondent are strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 16 participants “Strongly Agree” that “Leaders should give direct feedback about performance” and “Agree” was chosen by 12 respondents, meanwhile 6 participants are neutral, and 1 participant strongly disagree. Beside the result that, there are 15 participants “Agree” that “Leaders should ask for feedback on your leadership”, 11 respondents strongly Agree, while 7 participants are neutral and 1 participant disagree, whereas 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent strongly disagree. It was also shown that

there are 16 participants agree that “Leaders should be open to new ideas” while 14 respondents strongly agree, other 3 respondents neutral and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Lastly, there are 14 respondents responded strongly agree that “Leaders should understand your own motivation” same as 14 respondents are strongly agreed, while 5 more respondents are neutral and the other 2 respondents are strongly disagreed.

Section III – Skill, Knowledge and attitude toward to educational leadership

A. Skill.

Based on 35 respondents, the result shown that 14 respondents agree that personnel Management Skills, 10 respondents respond neutral, while other 9 respondents chose strongly agree and other 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent are strongly disagreed. Additionally, there are 16 respondents agree that “General Management Skills”, whereas other 11 respondents respond strongly agree but another 5 respondents neutral, other 2 respondents disagree and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 17 respondents agree that “Management of Financial Resources”, while 11 respondents responded neutral, another 6 respondents strongly agree and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Besides that, there are 22 respondents agree that “Management of Material Resources”, while other 6 respondents strongly agree same as another 6 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. In other hand, there are 15 respondents agree that “Cognitive skill” while 12 respondents responded strongly agree, while 6 respondents are neutral and 1 respondent is strongly Disagree. It was also observed that, there are 13 respondents strongly agree that “Interpersonal Skills”, 12 respondents responded agree, while other 9 respondents selected “Neutral” and 1 respondent are strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 16 participants

“Agree” that “Strategic Skills” and “Strongly Agree” was chosen by 12 respondents, meanwhile 5 participants are neutral, 1 respondent responded disagree and 1 participant strongly disagree. Beside the result that, there are 14 participants “Strongly agree” that “Personal value”, 12 respondents chose agree, while 7 participants are neutral and 2 participants strongly disagree. It was also shown that there are 12 participants strongly agree that “Communication skill” same as 12 respondents agree, while other 6 respondent’s neutral, 4 respondents responded disagree and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Lastly, there are 18 respondents responded strongly agree that “Decision-Making skill” while 11 respondents are agreed, but other 5 respondents are neutral and 1 respondent is strongly disagreed.

B. Knowledge

Based on 35 respondents, the result shown that 14 respondents strongly agree that Leaders in education and elsewhere have power and influence to change the culture of organization and to overcome cognitive a group in order to work towards valuing diversity, same as 14 respondents respond agree, while other 5 respondents chose neutral and other 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent are strongly disagreed. Additionally, there are 18 respondents agree that “Leadership in education needs to run deep, ensuring that all members of the school community and their perspectives are included fairly in all school processes”, whereas other 11 respondents respond strongly agree but another 5 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 18 respondents agree that “Educational Leaders have a great responsibility. First of all, they should manage the crisis by planning the risks. A good leader reduces the negative effects of pandemic by planning what many go wrong and make alternative plans”, while 11 respondents responded strongly agree,

but another 4 respondents neutral, other 1 respondent disagree and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Besides that, there are 20 respondents agree that “educational leaders develop strategies that allow them space and opportunities to measure up such demands against their values and principles” while 10 respondents strongly agree, but the other 3 are neutral, 1 respondent responded disagree and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Lastly, there are 17 respondents responded strongly agree that “Educational leaders need to be effective communicators with individual and group -especially in articulating and transmitting their ideas and vision”, while other 12 respondents strongly agree, while another 5 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree.

A. Attitude

Based on 35 respondents, the result shown that 14 respondents agree that “ if I disagree, I usually let other know”, while 12 respondents respond neutral, but the other 7 respondents chose strongly agree, 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent are strongly disagreed. Additionally, there are 12 respondents strongly agree that “I am willing to take more risks than most of my peers”, same as 12 respondents respond agree, while other 10 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 17 respondents agree that “it’s easy for me to make friends”, while 10 respondents responded neutral, but another 6 respondents strongly agree, while other 1 respondent disagree and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Besides that, there are 18 respondents agree that “I take the time to look at all the facts before making decision” while 9 respondents strongly agree, but the other 7 are neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Lastly, there are 18 respondents responded agree that “I am strategic and future-focused”, while other 8 respondents strongly agree, same as another 8 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree.

Section IV – High quality and paid job in educational leadership

According to the survey with 35 respondents, the result has shown that 15 respondents strongly agree that establish yourself as an expert in your field, 13 respondents responded agree, while other 5 respondents chose neutral, but another 1 respondent disagree and 1 respondent are strongly disagreed. Additionally, there are 17 respondents agree that “Make professional connections”, whereas other 12 respondents respond strongly agree but another 5 respondents neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 15 respondents agree that “Create cross-training opportunities for yourself to expand your skill set”, while 11 respondents responded strongly agree another 7 respondents neutral, other 1 respondent disagree and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Besides that, there are 21 respondents agree that “Develop your leadership skills outside your job by taking an executive position at a professional association or nonprofit”, while other 8 respondents chose strongly agree, but another 6 respondents are neutral and 1 respondent strongly disagree. In other hand, there are 14 respondents strongly agree that “Push yourself outside your comfort zone and act as a problem solver who can take on challenges and turn them into accomplishments” while 13 respondents responded agree, while 6 respondents are neutral, other 1 respondent is disagreed and 1 respondent is strongly Disagree. It was also observed that, there are 16 respondents agree that “Use your new responsibilities at your current job to make it your new higher-paying job by seeking out a raise that aligns with your new workload”, 9 respondents responded strongly agree, while other 8 respondents selected “Neutral”, other 1 respondent is disagreed and 1 respondent are strongly disagree. Furthermore, there are 15 participants “Agree” that “taking a position that has you managing a team shows valuable leadership skills” and

“Strongly Agree” was chosen by 10 respondents, meanwhile 8 participants are neutral, 1 respondent responded disagree and 1 participant strongly disagree. Beside the result that, there are 16 participants strongly agree that “Being willing to face the disappointment of being turned down may open up a door you otherwise would not have thought passable”, 9 respondents chose neutral, while 8 participants are strongly agreed, other 1 participant disagree and 1 respondent strongly disagree. It was also shown that there are 15 participants agree that “Creating your own online presence to show off your work skill is an ideal way to build a portfolio” meanwhile 9 respondents responded neutral, but another 8 respondents strongly agree, 2 respondents responded disagree and other 1 respondent strongly disagree. Lastly, there are 13 respondents responded agree that “Pick up valuable skills by attending lecturers or classes at the convention to improve your performance” while 12 respondents are strongly agreed, but other 8 respondents are neutral, 1 respondent chose disagree and 1 respondent is strongly disagreed.

- **Research Question 1:** What are the best models of used educational leadership?

According to the research question one that I let BELTEI IU lecturer/director/dean-vice dean/ team management answer, I received the answers from them as well. There are two questions in this research question one such as 1. What is the best model of educational leadership that you need to improve or develop? 2. Do you think that Communication skill is important to develop educational leadership in higher education?” I would like to sum up the answers as follows: (1). what is the best model of educational leadership that you need to improve or develop? Based on participants’ answers, the best models of used in educational leadership which they have mentioned the most is the Democratic leadership style, second is the

Transformational Leadership, third is Autocratic, fourth is Laissez-Faire, Charismatic and transitional leadership style. In this question, the participants also have mentioned that as a leader should have Communication skill, Interpersonal skills, coaching skill, motivated skill and the ability to adjust and adapt, accept in any situation. As leaders also need to have new knowledge and new experience because this has been found as one of the best educational leadership styles in terms of students' performance? By working with teachers to improve their skills through coaching, the school leaders help in strengthening the school's grasp on educational quality. (2). Do you think that Communication skill is important to develop educational leadership in higher education? According to the answers from the respondents, most of them have agreed that the Communication skill is important to develop educational leadership in higher education because communication skill is essential to develop educational leadership in higher education. Communication is key to building relationships and trust between faculty, staff, and students, as well as collaborating with other institutions. Moreover, effective communication can help build consensus and lead to successful decision-making and policy formation. Communication]is becoming essentials as the principal who plays role as the school leader, will need to be able to align his/her values with those of the organization to accomplish their goals in making a quality school as it a tool to work effectively with people. Sometimes, communications should be smooth communication between a leader and subordinates.

- **Research Question 2:** How do you develop a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education?

According to the research question two that I let BELTEI IU lecturer/director/dean-vice dean/ team

management answer, I received the answers from them as well. There are two questions in this research question one such as 1. Why Autocratic leadership style and Democratic leadership style in university/organization should be needed in developing a guiding model of educational leadership? 2. Which model below do you think that should be needed to develop as an educational leader? Why?" I would like to go over the main points the answers as follows :(1). Why Autocratic leadership style and Democratic leadership style in university/organization should be needed in developing a guiding model of educational leadership?

Based on participants' answers, they have given the reason why Autocratic leadership style and Democratic leadership style in university/organization should be needed in developing a guiding model of educational leadership, the first reason: in a democratic leadership style, a school principal always includes teachers in every decision making so that it can improve teacher performance which will affect the achievement of educational goals and the quality of education; second reason: these two styles are effective in different situations. An autocratic style can be used when there is a need for quick decision making and a lack of time for debate.

It is also effective in ensuring that all expectations are met. A democratic style can be used when there is a need for collaborative decision making, shared problem solving, and team building. Both of these styles can be used to ensure that the desired objectives of a university or organization are achieved. Additionally, these styles can be used to help create a strong culture of communication, collaboration, and trust; Third reason: in a university principal always includes teachers in every decision making so one style cannot apply for all situations and it's also allows staff to focus on performing specific tasks without worrying about making complex decisions and to become

highly skilled at performing certain duties, which can be beneficial to the organization; it's the way that leader in company needs to decide what to do or what to lead the whole team; fourth reason: It's more into how to organize and manage better strategy to improve leadership skill and personal development when work with different people, difference tactic and leadership need to work Auto depend on mission and goals of organization, when you are a leader you're not depending on your group but it depends on you see what is the vision and mission of the organization, so leadership could make better decision making based on their follower as well. (2). which model below do you think that should be needed to develop as an educational leader? Why?

According to the answers from the respondents, most of them have chosen Democratic leadership style because the people have a more participatory role in the decision making process. One person retains final say over all decisions but allows others to share insight and ideas. This is often a highly effective form of leadership. People are more likely to excel in their positions and develop more skills when they feel empowered, and people are empowered when they are involved in the decision-making process. Although it may take some time to achieve full participation from a group, the end result will be rewarding if you can manage to establish a power-sharing environment in your group project. You will find that democratic practices often lead to a more productive and higher quality work group. Second, they have chosen Transformational leadership because this style is essential for educational leaders to cultivate an environment of trust and collaboration in the classroom and school. Leaders who embrace transformational leadership create a culture of innovation and inclusivity, encouraging teachers, staff and students to actively participate in school decisions, problem solving and creative thinking. Transformational

leadership also emphasizes continuous learning, so educators are continually motivated to expand their knowledge and skills and grow professionally. They also mentioned to the other style such as Autocratic, transactional, Laissez-Faire, Charismatic Leadership and others. When situations change frequently, all leadership style can offer a great deal of flexibility to adapt to better ways of doing things.

• **Research Question 3:** Why educational leadership should be reputable in Higher Education?

According to the research question three that I let BELTEI IU lecturer/director/dean-vice dean/ team management answer, I also received the answers from them. There is only one question in this research question one such as 1. What do you expect to enhance a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education in the 21st century?" I would like to go over the main points the answers as follows: (1). what do you expect to enhance a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education in the 21st century? Based on participants' answers, the most of expectation to enhance a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education in the 21st century is the modern leadership with high effective technology in order to enhance a guiding model of educational leadership in higher education in the 21st century, educational leaders must possess the ability to lead and collaborate across

disciplinary boundaries, influence others through a shared vision of the future, employ strategies that promote diversity, inclusion and equity, and leverage technology to facilitate collaborative learning. Additionally, leaders must understand the changing needs of their students, support and nurture innovation, utilize evidence-based practices, focus on the development of holistic approaches to teaching and learning, and ensure accountability for outcomes. Moreover, an effective model must include communication and dialogue with stakeholders, embrace student-centered approaches, and recognize and foster a culture of creativity and risk-taking. Finally, it is essential for educational leaders to embrace global connectivity and ensure that curricula are current and relevant to the 21st century. Leaders should have all these skills because all skill represents just the starting point on the path towards mastering 21st century leadership skills. These include critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, communication and collaboration. They describe how school leaders approach complex challenges. They also expect to see all of students who graduated can learn more the ideas of being a good leader and they could lead the university, school or any organization which they work with to get good benefit from being a good leader by using a good model of leadership in their own career in the future.

Findings

Table 1: Section I

No.	Section I	Category (Demographic Profiles)
1	8.6%	age category (37 – 45, 45 and above 45 years)
2	31.4%	female
3	2.9%	Working at BIU campus 2
4	2.9%	Position Job (Director-Deputy Director)
5	11.4%	Working at BIU from (4-5 years)
6	2.9%	No (Do you think Educational leadership is important for those who are studying in higher education?)
7	28.6%	No (Have you ever been train to be as a leader before you start working?)
8	8.6%	Have been working as leader for (6 years or more)

Total	97.3%	Sum: $\frac{97.3 \times 8}{100} = 7.78\%$
-------	-------	---

Table 2: Section II

No.	Section II	Category (Quality Assessment as a guiding Model of Educational Leadership)
Model 1: characteristic of leadership		
1	2.9%	Flexible and do as a model or as an example for others
2	2.9%	Leaders have a long-term, deep impact on their communities and nations.
3	2.9%	Leaders can and do make a difference in the strength of their institutions
4	2.9%	Leaders also practice key behaviors on a regular basis
5	5.7%	Leaders are self-aware and prioritize personal development
6	2.9%	Leaders adapt to whether an individual or group is ready
7	2.9%	Leaders encourage strategic thinking, innovation, and action
8	2.9%	Leaders consider the ethical consequences of the decisions
9	2.9%	Leaders are able to clearly communicate with individuals
Total	28.9%	Sum: $\frac{28.9 \times 9}{100} = 2.60\%$
Model 2: role of a good leader		
1	2.9%	Leaders should engage in honest, open communication.
2	2.9%	Leaders should connect with your team members
3	2.9%	Leaders should encourage personal and professional growth
4	2.9%	Leaders should keep a positive attitude
5	2.9%	Leaders should teach employees instead of giving orders
6	2.9%	Leaders should set clear employee goals and expectations
7	2.9%	Leaders should give direct feedback about performance
8	2.9%	Leaders should ask for feedback on your leadership
9	2.9%	Leaders should be open to new ideas
10	5.7%	Leaders should understand your own motivation
Total	31.8%	Sum: $\frac{31.8 \times 10}{100} = 3.18\%$

Table 3: Section III

No.	Section III	Category (Skill, Knowledge and attitude toward to educational leadership)
Skill		
1	2.9%	Personnel Management Skills
2	2.9%	General Management Skills
3	2.9%	Management of Financial Resources
4	2.9%	Management of Material Resources
5	5.7%	Cognitive Skill
6	2.9%	Interpersonal Skills
7	2.9%	Strategic Skills
8	5.7%	Personal Values
9	2.9%	Communication
10	2.9%	Decision-making
Total	34.6%	Sum: $\frac{34.6 \times 10}{100} = 3.4\%$
Knowledge		
		Personnel Management Skills
1	2.9%	Leaders in education and elsewhere have power
2	2.9%	Leadership in education needs to run deep,
3	2.9%	Educational leaders have a great responsibility.
4	2.9%	Educational leaders develop strategies

5	2.9%	Educational leaders need to be effective communicators
Total	14.5%	Sum: $\frac{14.5 \times 5}{100} = 0.72\%$
Attitude		
1	2.9%	If I disagree, I usually let others know.
2	2.9%	I am willing to take more risks than most of my peers
3	2.9%	It's easy for me to make friends
4	2.9%	I take the time to look at all the facts before making decisions.
5	2.9%	I am strategic and future-focused.
Total	14.5%	Sum: $\frac{14.5 \times 5}{100} = 0.72\%$

Table 4: Section IV

No.	Section IV	Category (High quality and paid job in educational leadership)
1	2.9%	Establish yourself as an expert in your field
2	2.9%	Make professional connections
3	2.9%	Create cross-training opportunities for yourself to expand your skill set
4	2.9%	Develop your leadership skills outside your job
5	2.9%	Push yourself outside your comfort zone and act as a problem solver
6	2.9%	Use your new responsibilities at your current job
7	2.9%	Taking a position that has you managing a team
8	2.9%	Being willing to face the disappointment of being turned down
9	2.9%	Creating your own online presence to show off your work
10	2.9%	Pick up valuable skills by attending lectures or classes
Total	29%	Sum: $\frac{29 \times 10}{100} = 2.9\%$

Table 5: Demographic results, I, II, III and IV

No.	Section I	Category (Demographic Profiles)
1	68.6%	female
2	71.4%	Working at BIU campus I
3	97.1%	YES (Do you think Educational leadership is important for those who are studying in higher education?)
4	71.4%	YES (Have you ever been train to be as a leader before you start working?)
Total	308.5%	Sum: $\frac{308.5 \times 4}{100} = 12.3\%$

Table 6: Section II

No.	Section II	Category (Quality Assessment as a guiding Model of Educational Leadership)
Model 1: characteristic of leadership		
1	51.4%	Flexible and do as a model or as an example for others
2	60%	Leaders consider the ethical consequences of the decisions
Total	111.4%	Sum: $\frac{111.4 \times 2}{100} = 2.22\%$
Model 2: role of a food leader		
1	60%	Leaders should connect with your team members
2	48.6%	Leaders should teach employees instead of giving orders
Total	108.6%	Sum: $\frac{108.6 \times 2}{100} = 2.17\%$

Table 7: Section III

No.	Section III	Category (Skill, Knowledge and attitude toward to educational
-----	-------------	---

leadership)		
Skill		
1	62.9%	Management of Material Resources
2	51.4%	Decision-making
Total	114.3%	Sum: $\frac{114.3 \times 2}{100} = 4.8\%$
Knowledge		
1	57.1%	Educational leaders develop strategies that allow them space
2	48.6%	Educational leaders need to be effective communicators
Total	105.7%	Sum: $\frac{105.7 \times 3}{100} = 2.28\%$
Attitude		
1	51.4%	I take the time to look at all the facts before making decisions
2	51.4%	I am strategic and future-focused
Total	102.8%	Sum: $\frac{102.84 \times 2}{100} = 2.05\%$

Table 8: Section IV

No.	Section IV	Category (High quality and paid job in educational leadership)
1	48.6%	Make professional connections
2	60%	Develop your leadership skills outside your job
Total	108.6%	Sum: $\frac{108.6 \times 2}{100} = 2.17\%$

Table 9: Section I-IV Comparisons

No.		Strengthen	weakness	Solutions
1	Section I	34.3%	8.6%	For the section I, personally, BIU should provide training course about school leader or educational leadership to people who work in their organization before they start working because it could help them know how to teach student, coaching/guiding their students.
2		68.6%	31.4%	
3		71.4%	2.9%	
4		45.7%	2.9%	
5		42.9%	11.4%	
6		97.1%	2.9%	
7		71.4%	28.6%	
8		65.7%	8.6%	
Total		Sum: $\frac{497.12 \times 8}{100} = 39.7\%$	Sum: $\frac{97.3 \times 8}{100} = 7.78\%$	
Section II				
		Model 1		For the section II, a person who working as a leader should be flexible and do as a model or as an example for others, leader also should adapt to whether an individual the most model that leaders need to have consider the ethical consequences of the decisions that they make for both their customers and their teams.
1	51.4%	2.9%		
2	48.6%	2.9%		
3	45.7%	2.9%		
4	51.4%	2.9%		
5	42.9%	5.7%		
6	51.4%	2.9%		
7	45.7%	2.9%		
8	60%	2.9%		
9	42.9%	2.9%		
Total		Sum: $\frac{440 \times 9}{100} = 39.6\%$	Sum: $\frac{28.9 \times 9}{100} = 2.6\%$	
Section II				
		Model 2		
1	45.7%	2.9%		Being a good leader

2		60%	2.9%	should connect with your team members and should encourage personal and professional growth. Sometime, a good leader also should teach employees instead of giving orders to your team. Being a good listener and be open to the new ideas.
3		48.6%	2.9%	
4		45.7%	2.9%	
5		48.6%	2.9%	
6		40%	2.9%	
7		45.7%	2.9%	
8		42.9%	2.9%	
9		45.7%	2.9%	
10		40%	5.7%	
Total		Sum: $\frac{462.9 \times 10}{100} = 49.29\%$	Sum: $\frac{318 \times 10}{100} = 3.18\%$	
	Section III	Skill		For section three, the most skill that leaders should have the ability to manage the material resources and manage the finance resources, second is a decision making in every situation. Because all these skills help a lot for those who are working as a leader to have ability to guide, manage, develop and influence their follower in any level.
1		40%	2.9%	
2		45.7%	2.9%	
3		48.6%	2.9%	
4		62.9%	2.9%	
5		42.9%	5.7%	
6		37.1%	2.9%	
7		45.7%	2.9%	
8		40%	5.7%	
9		34.3%	2.9%	
10		51.4%	2.9%	
Total		Sum: $\frac{448.6 \times 10}{100} = 44.86\%$	Sum: $\frac{34.6 \times 10}{100} = 3.46\%$	
	Section III	Knowledge		Educational leaders should have a great responsibility. First of all, they should manage the crisis by planning the risk, a good leader has to reduce the negative effects of pandemic by planning what may go wrong and make alternative plans.
1		40%	2.9%	
2		51.4%	2.9%	
3		51.4%	2.9%	
4		57.1%	2.9%	
5		48.6%	2.9%	
Total		Sum: $\frac{248.5 \times 5}{100} = 12.42\%$	Sum: $\frac{14.5 \times 5}{100} = 0.77\%$	
	Section III	Attitude		Being an educational leader, having a good attitude is the best way to solve any problem and can be the person who in their team believe and be willing to follow to pursue the same goal for successful in the future together.
1		40%	2.9%	
2		34.3%	2.9%	
3		48.6%	2.9%	
4		51.4%	2.9%	
5		51.4%	2.9%	
Total		Sum: $\frac{225.7 \times 5}{100} = 11.28\%$	Sum: $\frac{14.5 \times 5}{100} = 0.77\%$	
1	Section IV	42.9%	2.9%	For section four, to get high quality and paid job in educational leadership, first they should develop their leadership skill outside their job, making aa professional connection it could help a

				lot to get a new the opportunity with higher position.
2		48.6%	2.9%	
3		42.9%	2.9%	
4		60%	2.9%	
5		40%	2.9%	
6		45.7%	2.9%	
7		42.9%	2.9%	
8		45.7%	2.9%	
9		42.9%	2.9%	
10		37.1%	2.9%	
Total		Sum: $\frac{448.7 \times 10}{100} = 44.87\%$	Sum: $\frac{29 \times 10}{100} = 2.9\%$	

Summary of Findings

The questionnaire has 20 questions that aimed to get lecturers, managers, director and team leaders' opinions on the model of leadership and to be a role of good leader. According to the results, all of the kinds, including characteristic and a role model are seen favorably leadership issues. Knowing the perceptual outcomes for each kind would allow the researcher to decide on the outcome. As a result of the research and conclusions made above, it was discovered that BELTEI International University lecturers, managers, directors and team leaders did not have a big issue in leading. The overall mean also indicated that it was agreed. It indicated that the lecturers, managers, directors encountered issues on sometimes with some types. The findings of this study will help lectures/manager/directors and students succeed in being a good leader in their career and be able to guide or lead their team in the good way without any issue in their organizations. Lecturers/Students who are proficient in using any style of leadership can have more power and credit than lecturer/students who lack these skills. The study's findings can also be used to be a guiding model of their leadership skill in their current positions. Lecturers/Students can be prepared to discover a solution to ensure the success of their skill when they have a comprehensive understanding of those influencing elements. It acts as a compass to direct lecturers/students toward leading skill to achieve their goal. Finally, this study identified the most effective leadership model that lecturers/ students employ when learning to be a leader. The perception of the lecturers/students toward leadership model was examined in 55 questions, with particular attention paid to the democratic leadership model that students employ in general, those that they employ before to be a leader and those that they employ during leading. Lecturers/Students employ effective leadership model to develop their

leadership abilities based on the results of their coursework. With these many foci and statistical methods, the study's conclusions will have the biggest impact on me and all future generations of students who wish to pursue a good leader with the effective ability.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to analyze the lecturers/managers/directors and team leaders' perception of developing a guiding model of educational leadership from campus 1 and campus 2 of BELTEI International University. Based on the findings and discussion, as a researcher of BELTEI International University, I greatly value the respondents' responses. The findings of this study showed that the characteristic, skill, knowledge and attitude which good leaders should be and practice to develop their ability and knowledge about leadership. According to the result from the study about all kinds of leadership style such as characteristic, role of good model, skill, knowledge and attitude of leadership showed that the lecturers/managers/directors did not have a big issue on leadership skills. Moreover, most of the lecturer have been practicing the model of leadership such as the democratic, autocratic, transactional leadership style before start working as a leader, during being a leader, after being a leader in higher position that were introduced by training/learning to enhance their leadership skills actively. The results of this finding provide the useful information to BIU lecturers/managers/directors because it mainly focuses on developing the guiding model of educational leadership by all leaders in leading their students or their staffs. When lecturers/managers/directors clearly know about model of leadership in leading people, they can be ready to solve the problem or conflict and the way how to sue the tools to control their staff to make their leading successful. In addition, this study benefits to students to enlarge better

understanding of leadership skills effectively by examining of what determined through the concept of lecturers/managers/directors. Finally, it also gives benefits to researcher to gain more experiences about the guiding or modeling of educational leadership.

Recommendations

Some lecturers/managers/directors prefer using leadership style for their own way, but we all know how difficult it is in the modern world, therefore, sometimes it is wiser using the mix of leadership style to entrust them with the best sample model. Although the conclusion above showed the positivity, there were some suggestions proposed. Firstly, certain leadership practices such as networking, calmness and compassion are more connected to educational leadership for BELTEI International University. This study indicates that university students need to stay connected and informed within online communities and they request more transparency in which leaders openly share both good and unfavorable developments and give feedback which in turn hopefully strengthens trust and organizational culture between followers and leader. Most of the participants expect from educational leaders to create supportive and inclusive learning environment, construct feedback for improvement, create a vision of academic success and provide resources for learning. Secondly, enhancing educational practices is a potentially significant concept within a higher education institution context and educational leadership is connected to achieving institutional goals and academic development. University suggest that it needs to be a part of educational leadership to accomplish the goals of department, curriculum and to contribute to the visions of school organization. Also, another key feature of educational leadership is calmness and compassion during pandemic, in which students profoundly need educational leaders to lead under

pressure, emphasize optimism, care for learners, and inspire for learning. Lastly, analytical and strategical thinking is still important for educational leadership for the new normal as the educational leadership generally requires making data-driven decisions, risk-planning of the instructional and organizational process

References

- Bennis, W. (1992) *On Becoming a Leader*, London: Addison-Wesley.
- Beatriz, P., Deborah, N., & Hopkins, D. (2008). *Improving School leadership*. BELTEI International University. (2021). Retrieved from BELTEI International University: <http://www.beltei.edu.kh>
- Cosenza, M. N. (2015). *Defining Teacher Leadership Affirming the Teacher Leader Model Standards*. Issue in teacher education, 82.
- D. Goleman, R. Boyatzis, A. McKEE. (2002). *Primal Leadership*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Educational Leadership. (2015). Cambridge International Examinations.
- Gümüş, S. (2018). *Educational Management Administration and leadership*. In S. B. Gümüş, A systematic review of studies of Leadership models in educational research from 1980 to 2014 (pp. 25-48). Egitim Bilimleri Bolümü, Konya 42090, Turkey.
- Kapur, R. (2018, March 11). *Educational Leadership*. Retrieved from ResearchGate: <http://www.researchgate.net>
- Kapur, R. (2018, March 11). *Educational Leadership*. Retrieved from ResearchGate: <http://www.researchgate.net>
- Leadership Model. (2020). Retrieved from The Wing institute: <https://www.winginstitute.org/quality-leadership-leadership-models>
- Peter, L. (2019). *Educational Development and Leadership in Higher education*. London and New York: RoutledgeFalmer.
- Phnom Penh. (2021, November 22). Retrieved from Wikipedia web site: <http://www.wikipedia.org>

Santivong, T. (2550). *The organization and Administrations*. Thailand, Bangkok: Wattana Panich.

Şenol, H. (2019). *Professional Development of Educational Leaders*. Famagusta, North Cyous: IntechOpen.

Smith, B. L. (2006). Leadership in higher education—its evolution and potential: A unique role facing. In *Leadership in higher education* (p. 157).

Tomlinson, H. (2004). *Educational Leadership*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.